

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Galatan**FIRST NAME:** Bogdan**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: no plagiarism detected

The author used the following software: MS Word on Office 365

List your five key concepts with the page number in the text:

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
5. Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42)

THE BASICS FOR ACADEMIC WRITING: RESPONSE PAPERS AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

Applying and getting accepted into a Ph.D. program is a privilege and a great responsibility at the same time. Once the initial hype of getting accepted washes over, the level of maturity and competence that is expected along the Ph.D. candidacy syncs in, and when starting the program, the joy of being a student again is mingled with the level of technical academic writing expected at the Ph.D. level.

Studying the subject, if you are interested in researching and gaining niche knowledge in the field, can be very exciting, but to get there, you must be able to write and publish papers at a high academic level.

Thus, the ACA-401D course is the writing foundation for all the rest of the courses, in my case, the DDIA program. The writing course is based on many technicalities and calls for strict rules that must be followed to succeed in future writing.

The topics that are important to master at the end of this course are essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, style guide, and the type of English chosen to follow, that being American or British, and this is to broadly mention the few aspects that are discussed in detail by the course documentation available for study. The topics discussed and approached in detail in this RP are paramount to understanding academic writing.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Writing an essay takes some good organizational skills, and I learned that the scrutiny applied at Ph.D. level writing is quite exigent and necessary to produce quality publications. Following the methodology used by the course instructors Cleenewerck and Gulma, a student's future writing and academic and non-academic writing styles can be defined.

Essay writing guides towards staying organized and creating a timeline, from inception to handing in the work to be evaluated. An important aspect that the coursepack points out is that it prompts the writer to ask self-reflecting questions, such as if the topic is relevant, if the research can be used for argumentation, and to support one's answers in the event of an oral examination or a debate (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–12).

However, the instructions on how to write an essay, although they point toward a technically sound writing manner, do not question the element of meaningfulness of the topic. Throughout previous academic writings and research, I learned that it is much easier to write on a specific topic and research it quickly if it addresses something meaningful for the writer.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The chapter on punctuation is straightforward and contains many examples of what is considered correct and incorrect punctuation.

While these examples are easy to understand, the chapter needs to point out a methodology for using the punctuation rules without mechanically memorizing these aspects. For a writer to be able to master punctuation at the level described in the chapter, it is necessary to submerge into writing at a level that perhaps surpasses Ph.D. academic writing needs.

In this case, the best approach to respecting the rigorous punctuation rules is to refer often to the chapter in the coursepack. It is beneficial that the student orientation and introductory materials help the students obtain a professional account with Grammarly. This software analyzes the technicality of the writing in real-time, offering suggestions for improvement and helping the writers respect punctuation.

Therefore, we owe some of the success of our writing to the software made available to assist us. Still, nevertheless, writers who perform this activity for a living, such

as journalists, technical writers, editors, and academics, can possess a level of technical punctuation that surpasses software capabilities.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

It is exciting to revisit how to pronounce and spell different words and expressions between American and British English. After having been taught British English in primary school throughout the end of high school, I moved to the U.S., where I lived, studied, and worked for the next fourteen years after high school before finally moving to France.

The differences between the same language are striking, especially when it comes to writing because this is when I experience some rare spelling conflicts between what I am used to utilizing as the day-to-day spelling for some of the American English words, but still remember the way I initially learned to spell the very same word when I was learning English.

The list described in the coursepack document is extensive and tied to the words and expressions used widely. For someone experiencing both styles of English, going through the list is a great exercise, and the fact that we are assisted by software in our writing is again of tremendous assistance (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32).

5) PLAGIARISM

As a rule, plagiarism is something that, at higher academic writing levels, you do not accidentally produce in a paper but rather deliberately.

The chapter on plagiarism is beneficial in knowing when and how to cite and paraphrase, with quoting and paraphrasing being the only tools to protect one writer against plagiarism. Plagiarism is not only an undesirable trait to have in one's paper, but it also contributes to the writer's reputation and overall perception by its readers and evaluators.

The authors of the coursepack have indicated not only what to do to avoid plagiarism in this extended chapter but also when not to produce citations in a response paper. This aspect is beneficial because it creates clarity for the writer in terms of not being overly cited in their paper, weakening the purpose and message of the paper itself due to a significantly elevated level of protection layer expressed through too many citations and references.

Cleenewerck and Gulma also define the concept of signal phrases as part of the plagiarism chapter, stating that "Using signal phrases introduces a quotation or paraphrase by using a verb and mentioning the author's name." For me, this represents a new and great learning in technical writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38).

6) STYLE GUIDE

Finally, we can observe the depth of technical academic writing by trying to understand the importance and sophistication of a style guide.

As the coursepack chapter mentions, style looks at technical aspects such as the length of sentences and paragraphs, punctuation, font choice, spelling, structure, etc. However, the weight of the style lies within the ability of readers to identify a writer by their writing style consistently.

Let us consider that a writer can reach the finesse of establishing and methodically using a style guide. In that case, the writer will gain the ability to develop a certain familiarity and intimacy with its readership, provided that the reader resonates with the writings of the same author.

Although the authors of the coursepack sustain that style guide is essential for freelance writers, at this moment, I cannot agree or disagree with the statement since I do not have the experience of comparing the information learned in the coursework with several writings of a freelance writer and be able to draw my conclusion on the matter. In the meantime, the writers of the style guide chapter are correct in their observation regarding freelance writers and style, given their advanced knowledge and experience in the field of technical and academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42).

7) CONCLUSION

The coursepack and its contents for Period 1 remain very demanding and technical, especially for returning students who have been away from the academic writing desk for a while.

However, I learned that although I took a critical thinking and writing course while in college, this course is several levels more advanced than what I have experienced before. I look forward to cementing some course concepts into future academic writings.

The depth of the course also confirms the quality required at the Ph.D. level, and everyone enrolled in a Ph.D. program is here voluntarily, thus ready and willing to spend quality time and effort producing excellent academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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